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THE VISITORS

DESIGNING MEDIA FACADES TO SUPPORT LINKS BETWEEN PEOPLE AND PLACES

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ABSTRACT

The pervasive integration of media façades in the urban environment challenges designers on how to use this new communication medium. There is a need for a framework to understand and approach this emergent field. This paper presents advances in our research work investigating how interaction, information interpretation and aesthetics interplay to influence and shape the way people perceive and understand the urban space digitally mediated by media façades. The article introduces theVISITORS, a design case that investigates how the links between people and places can be mediated by abstract audio-visual representations of people's presence and activity on a media façade. Our findings indicate that visually aesthetic, ambient, metaphoric, and artistically enhanced representations, which allow for sense-making, versatility, and openness for interpretation could be a valuable resource of design.

Keywords: shared spaces, media façades, interaction and information design

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays digital information is becoming more pervasive and intertwined with our daily activities. The constant evolution of ubiquitous computing has enabled the expanding use of digital technologies surrounding numerous aspects of human life beyond the workplace, including schools, museums, airports, squares, waiting rooms, etc. In the general scope of our research, we focus on the urban media screens that are constantly being integrated in various kinds of shared places. These dynamic digital displays vary from LED and plasma screens to projection surfaces as well as intelligent architectural surfaces and media facades (Struppek, 2006). For a long time, urban media screens have been primarily dominated by commercially motivated digital imagery, like advertisement of consumer goods or mass sports and music events, or by highly task-oriented activities (fig. 1), and their design has not interested academics until recently. However, the predominance of these types of interfaces can influence the attitude of people inhabiting the shared spaces and their behavior towards each other and the environment.

Figure 1. Media landscape in different urban settings: marked by functionalism and/or consumption

Sociologists and media theorist have argued that this behavior is marked by passivity and alienation and non-reflected consumption. (McQuire, 2007; Huhtamo, 2009). Instead, the urban media landscape should be the mediator for objectives like increasing the awareness, reflection and consciousness or/and enhancing the emotional relationships between people and places (Virilio, 1997; Manovich, 2006; Struppek, 2006; Lester, 2006).

Recently, there has been numerous initiatives to promote the aesthetic, social and communicative potential of large urban displays throughout experimental engagements from the art, games and media-architecture disciplines (a.o. Blinkenlights, 2001; Lozano-Hemmer, 2002; ag4 media façade GmbH, 2006; Urban Screens Association, 2008; Media Façade Festival, 2010). Although very valuable and inspiring in themselves, insights from those disciplines fail to address the need of a coherent framework of design guidelines, which would help the design research community and practitioners understand and approach this emergent field in a informed and consistent manner.

In our research, we aim to make a step towards such a framework by designing and studying large-scale media displays in different shared urban settings. Our work follows a research through design approach (Zimmermann et al., 2007) to investigate how aesthetics, interaction and interpretation interplay to influence the experience of interactive content in urban life, and understand how they eventually shape the way people perceive and understand environments digitally mediated by large-scale media.

This paper presents theVISITORS, a media Façade design case conceived to support emotional links between shared spaces of spontaneous human traffic and their visitors. This design case investigates how the links between people and places can be mediated by abstract audio-visual representations of people's presence and activity staged in a shared environment.

We start by describing the design criteria and decisions of the current iteration of our work. We later present our initial findings based on observations and in-situ interviews. Finally we discuss the implications for further designs.

DESIGN CRITERIA

As already suggested by our research motivation, we believe that large-scale media play a vital role in the perception of the spaces we inhabit and our understanding of the public sphere that embraces them. Successfully designed interactive content can augment the environment with digital information to further increase the positive relationship between people and places by supporting aesthetic and engaging experiences with the space.

Designing interactive content for media facades that supports the communicative goals and intentions of the façade is a challenging task (Dalsgaard and Halskov, 2010). Façades require information types and representations different from those used in personal computers or static media. Several aspects play a vital role in the perception of large-scale media displays and have an influential weight on the design process.

Figure 2. A close view at the projection of theVISITORS prototype, seamlessly integrated as a projection mapping onto an inner-architectural surface.

These aspects include the architectural, situational and contextual characteristics of the space, display-specific parameters such as scale, resolution, brightness and exposure. Additionally, content can be designed to evoke emotional responses and convey meaning - through visually aesthetic, metaphoric, and/or artistically enhanced representations - that leave room for open interpretation and discussion (Lau and Moere, 2007).

DESIGN DECISIONS

We designed the VISITORS as a large-scale projection and sound installation seamlessly integrated in the inner-architectural space of a shared place characterized by spontaneous human flow (like a large exhibition hall, the waiting hall of a station or hospital, or a passage).

Simple motion sensors placed in the shared space detect people's entering and leaving the space and cause the installation to produce subtle natural sounds (reproduced by hidden speakers). The human interactions within the space are also reflected in the animation of an aesthetic visual metaphor: a stylized subtly moving tree, populated by birds flying in and away upon passers-by entering and leaving (fig. 1).

We chose to consider the physical presence and activity of people as our data set because it can represent the interactions among people and the space in the most direct and sensorial way. Representation of this data could potentially allow for an increased perception and awareness. Furthermore, we relied upon the "animalistic" strategy for ambient media (Offenhuber, 2008) with a familiar, but yet surprising representation (birds), thus leaving space for open interpretation and discussion.

We integrated the display seamlessly in the space by mapping the projection onto the inner-architectural façade taking into consideration its physical form, thus providing for a more harmonic co-existence of the physical and digital artifacts and hence potentially increasing the success the facade's staging (ag4 media façade, 2006; Schoch, 2006).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The first version of the prototype was presented in an exhibition hall freely accessible to different kinds of audience (fig. 2). We studied peoples' reactions with respect to the media façade through observations and informal in-situ interviews.

SENSE-MAKING AND SENSE OF PLACE

Generally, the media façade was very well perceived by attendees, which were intrigued by the subtle sound response to their entering/leaving the space and could easily relate it to their "abstract" representation on the tree. Their comments and reactions showed amusement and curiosity, and they eagerly shared and explained the meaning of the installation to their companions. Some visitors were repeatedly entering and leaving or exaggeratedly passing through the hallway thus trying to interact with the different modes of the installation. In addition we have also talked to participants in the exhibition, who were actually space "inhabitants" (exhibitors or staff of the building) and not directly interested in interacting with the installation because of lack of time due to their own exhibitions responsibilities. They were usually walking in and out of the space, carrying out material for their own installations or standing around their stands and talking to other people. Those visitors also expressed an affective relationship through the installation by saying that with time "*it has turned out to be a delightful greeting for visitors*" and a "*playful way to represent human flow and activity*". One of them said "*I am glad that I am not constantly engaged with interacting with it, because I don't have time for that, but I appreciate it being there - it gives me the sense of being connected to the other visitors through the space*".

DATA VS. REPRESENTATION

As commented above, the one-to-one correspondence between a person's (dis)appearing from the space and the audio-visual representation (a short tweet sound, and a bird entering or leaving respectively), proved to be an effective mapping technique, with respect to making sense of the media facade. However, the auditory feedback became uncomfortable as human traffic increased, while the visual feedback - saturated. Future design

iterations will consider less direct, time-evolving and more interpretative mappings for both modalities. Besides contributing to a more harmonic design and enhanced ambientness, a design strategy, which avoids fast and immediate understanding, might also afford for long-terms reflection, “something to understand that has an interest in its own right” (Hallnäs and Redström, 2000).

DESIGN FOR VERSATILITY

Media façades face two main design challenges: designing for long-lasting engagement and designing for openness of interpretation (Dalsgaard and Halskov, 2010). In theVISITORS design case, we noticed that once visitors related to the representation and got used to it, they expected further information levels in their representation - one that would reflect the way they behave or move in the space. In future design iterations, we would like to consider the integration of versatile types of information considering aspects like *time* - reflecting visually the “timely history” of people’s activities in the shared space); *spatiality* - considering various spatial areas, directly or indirectly related to each other (i.e. the different floors or departments of a building), and encoding them in the visualization, and even *virtual presence* - integrating online activity information with regards to the shared space hosting the media façade - like related twitter activity or facebook participation.

Figure 3. The Visitors prototype deployed in an exhibition hall

OPENNESS FOR INTERPRETATION

Interestingly enough, in some cases passers-by created and mapped their own mental models that would describe or fit the birds’ behaviors in the visualization and tried to interact with the media façade accordingly. This agrees with previous findings with media façades, stating that people often “interpret” more causal relations between the representation and themselves (Dalsgaard and Halskov, 2010). That is, the design should afford “openness” (for interpretation) (Sengers and Gaver, 2006).

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The design case reveals some of the aspects that are important to consider when designing media facades and how these can be reflected and incorporated in the iterative design process. Our findings support the design criteria of designing for artistically enhanced but effective data mappings, which allow for affective but unobtrusive, ambient engagement with urban media façades. From this work we expect to collect further observations and empirical evidence on how multimodal visualization for media facades can be designed and how they are perceived. In particular, how theVISITORS installation changes the way passers-by behave and how it enhances the way they perceive their environment or shared space.

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